

The chemical make-up of the solar photosphere

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Relevance of the solar abundances

- Universal reference for chemistry
- Proximity gives us accurate parameters (mass, radius, hence surface gravity), and high-quality spectroscopic data
 - $M = 1.98847 \pm 0.00007 \times 10^{30} \text{ Kg}$
 - $R = 6.9566 \pm 0.0014 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$
 - **$\log g = 4.4381 \pm 0.0001$** (g in cgs)
 - **$T_{\text{eff}} = 5777 \pm 5 \text{ K}$**
- Spatially resolved data guide our modeling and help constrain uncertain parameters (granulation size/contrast, center-to-limb variation, absolute flux, bolometric flux...)

The Sun as a stellar reference

- Given the accuracy of the solar parameters, the Sun is the only star for which we can aspire to have the most accurate abundances

- Typically all stellar abundances are referred to the Sun

$$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = \log N(\text{Fe})/N(\text{H}) - \log [N(\text{Fe})/N(\text{H})]_{\text{sun}}$$

- Differential analysis (line-by-line) relative to the Sun can give superior precision (<0.01 dex), especially for solar-like stars, which can be translated to accuracy if the solar abundances are accurate

Meteoritic vs. photospheric

- Photospheric abundances are set as reference since limited mixing has taken place and the upper atmosphere is far harder to model
- Type I (Ivuna) carbonaceous chondrites appear to have preserved the original solar nebula composition (but see Asplund et al. 2021)
- Good agreement between their composition and the solar photosphere (using a refractory element such as Si)

Meteoritic vs. Photospheric

- But volatiles are missing: H, He, C, N, O....

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Spectroscopic abundance determinations

- Spectroscopic observations
- Radiative transfer
- Model atmospheres
- Fundamental (atomic/molecular) data
- Non-equilibrium line formation

Data

- The sun is hard(er) to observe
- Grating spectrographs (Liege atlas, SST, PEPISI)
- FTS atlases (Kitt Peak MacMath, IAG)
- New-generation ultra stable grating spectrographs (HARPS, ESPRESSO — Sun observed through the moon or asteroids)

A detailed comparison of the most recent high-quality data is missing

Model atmospheres

- Traditionally models assume:
 - hydrostatic equilibrium
 - local thermodynamical equilibrium
 - and radiative equilibrium
 - + mixing-length convection
- Solar observations show that hydrostatic equilibrium does not hold

Mancha simulations
(Khomenko group)

Model atmospheres

- Hydrodynamical simulations solve simple 1D convection approx. and the need for micro/macroturbulence but require simplifications in handling radiative heating
- LTE believed to have a minimal effect on atmospheric structure for a solar-like star
- Effect of magnetic field could be important: 0.03-0.11 dex corrections depending on the line for Fe I (Fabbian et al. 2012)

Allende Prieto et al. (2009)

- Hydrodynamical models reproduce line asymmetries and shapes, although beware of systematic errors in high layers

Radiative transfer

- Various solvers give slight / different values, generally ignored since differences are reduced when dealing with normalized spectra
- Computing the populations for molecules and atoms is not trivial: molecule formation affects the atoms, and departures from LTE affect atomic populations directly
- NLTE computations require detailed modeling of all the relevant processes: radiative and collisional

Fundamental data

- Ionization and excitation energies
- partition functions
- Molecular dissociation constants
- Radiative transition probabilities
- Damping constants
- Electron and hydrogen collisional rates

Golden rules of the spectroscopist

- Use relatively weak lines, strong enough for S/N and minimize blends, insensitive to microturbulence and damping constants, but with cores that don't get too high
- Use line profiles (as opposed to equivalent widths)
- Use the right number of lines: less is more (blending always makes your abundances higher)
- Evaluate the quality of your observations: if two available differ, examine them critically
- Use hydrodynamical models if available
- Evaluate (critically) departures from LTE consistently with your model atmosphere
- Search for the most recent fundamental data and compare with previous versions

Solar abundances

- He cannot be measured directly from the solar spectrum
- Li is depleted
- Be and B should be improved
- C, N and O will be discussed below
- Ne cannot be measured directly, but important for interior opacity (see recent changes by Young 2018 and the discussion by Asplund et al. 2021)
- Fe currently every one seems to have converged to $\sim 7.50 \pm 0.05$
- F and Cl should be improved (derived from spot spectra of hydrides)
- Ag and probably others should be revisited

Carbon and oxygen — 20 years ago

- Oxygen

Pre-2000 values ~ 8.8-8.9

Proposed 8.69 from [OI] 630 nm line (AP+ 2001)

Asplund et al. (2004) arrived at 8.66 from multiple indicators

- Carbon

Pre-2000 value ~ 8.6

Proposed 8.39 from [CII] 872.7 nm line (AP+ 2002)

Asplund et al. (2005) arrived at 8.39 from multiple indicators

Carbon

- Caffau et al. 2010 — 8.50 ± 0.06 (3D, atomic lines)
- Alexeeva & Mashonkina 2015 — 8.43—8.45 (CH, C₂, CI; 1D models)
- Amarsi et al. 2019 — 8.44 ± 0.02 , updated with f-values from Li et al. (2021) — 8.46 ± 0.02 (15 atomic lines; 3D NLTE)
- Amarsi et al. 2021 — 8.47 ± 0.02 (C₂, CH, CO)
- Magg et al. 2022 — 8.56 ± 0.06 (<3D>=1D, 3 atomic lines, LTE)

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Nitrogen

- Amarsi et al. 2021 — 7.89 ± 0.04 (NH, CN)
- Amarsi et al. 2020 — 7.77 ± 0.05 (5 atomic lines, 3D NLTE)
- Magg et al. 2022 — 7.97 ± 0.1 (<3D>=1D, 2 atomic lines)

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- Amarsi et al. 2021 — 7.89 ± 0.04 (NH, CN)
- Amarsi et al. 2020 — 7.77 ± 0.05 (5 atomic lines, 3D NLTE)
- Magg et al. 2022 — 7.97 ± 0.1 (<3D>=1D, 2 atomic lines)

Oxygen

- Steffen + 2015 — 8.75 (KP FTS) — 8.77 (8.77 (SST) (atomic, 3D, Drawin approximation for H collisions)
- Amarsi et al. 2018 — 8.69 ± 0.03 (atomic IR triplet, 3D new mod. for H coll.)
- Amarsi et al. 2021 — 8.70 ± 0.04 (OH lines)
- Asplund et al. 2021 — 8.69 ± 0.04 (more atomic lines + OH)
- Bergemann et al. 2021 — 8.75 (8.74 for the triplet, 8.77 for [OI] 630 nm) (atomic, 3D)
- Magg et al. 2022 — 8.77 ± 0.04 ($\langle 3D \rangle = 1D$, atomic lines)

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Atomic vs molecular

Atomic lines

Molecular lines

- | | | |
|--------------------|---|-------|
| • NLTE | - | + |
| • inhomogeneities | + | - |
| • Fundamental data | + | - (+) |
| • Number of lines | - | + |

Got to have them all

Conclusion: consistency between atomic and molecular indicators is a strong reason to prefer the low values

- Carbon: **8.46** (Amarsi+ 2019, Li+ 2021 for atomic lines), **8.47** (Amarsi+ 2021 for C2, CH, CN)
- Nitrogen: significant discrepancy between atomic and molecular lines (**7.77** vs **7.89**) — not a worry for stellar interior models
- Oxygen:
 - 8.69** (Amarsi+ 2018; Asplund et al. 2021) vs **8.74** (Bergemann+ 2021) from atomic lines
 - 8.70** from OH (Amarsi+ 2021)

Solar high-resolution (spatially-resolved) observations

- Bergemann et al. (2015) compare IAG, SST, Hinode and DST data finding differences of up to 0.06 dex in the derived oxygen abundances
- IAG can give up to 0.04 dex for higher abundance than SST for [OII] 630 nm, 0.02 dex for the IR triplet
- Steffen et al. (2015) compare FTS data from Kitt Peak McMath Facility to SST data set and find FTS data gives lower abundances by 0.01-0.03 dex
- A detailed/critical study is missing comparing with HARPS, PEPsi, ESPRESSO ...

